

The Effects Of Procrastination Practices On Deep Learning Approach Of MS Scholars At International Islamic University Islamabad

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Abstract

Procrastination is concerned with delaying or postponing tasks despite knowing the negative consequences. Procrastination is frequently faced by students due to different reasons. Procrastination has different styles in the learning approaches of students. The effects of procrastination on the deep learning approach of MS scholars are a common phenomenon that was usually not explored regarding its reasons, outcomes, and strategies. The use of different strategies to combat procrastination can lead students to perform better roles in life. The purpose of the present study was to discover possible strategies MS students use to overcome procrastination practices. The study also aimed to investigate the factors and effects of procrastination practices regarding the deep learning approach. The study was qualitative in nature. The population of the study was 22 female MS students of the Educational Leadership and Management department from the Faculty of Education at International Islamic University Islamabad. A sample of 14 students was selected through a random sampling technique from the first and second semesters of the MS ELM program. For collection of data, semi-structured interviews were conducted. The collected data was analyzed through thematic analysis. Major findings of the study revealed that the majority of the students at the university level are procrastinators. The main causes of procrastination were social media distraction, laziness, poor time management, perfectionism, socialization, and a lack of motivation. The results of the study revealed that procrastination has negative effects on the deep learning approach of students. The major effects of procrastination include increased workload, stress, poor performance, a sense of inferiority, and missing out on better opportunities. The study recommended that educators and students may take the responsibility to avoid procrastination by application of different strategies i.e., proper planning, Initiative, Task-oriented strategies, time management, and motivation to use their maximum potential. Future studies may be conducted on male students of private and public universities in Islamabad.

INTRODUCTION

Procrastination is the act of postponing or delaying tasks, premeditated tasks to a later time, typically without rational thinking (Balkis & Duru, 2009). Although procrastination practices are considered the most common fact and unfavorable feature, in education procrastination practices have detrimental effects across various aspects of life including loss of time, expanding stress on individuals, low grades, poor health, and affecting the long learning process and personal relations (Fuschia, 2022). There is a relationship between personality qualities and procrastination practices such as poor time management, lack of discipline, lethargy, and impulsiveness, resulting in feelings of regret for failing to complete tasks on time (George, 2017).

Procrastination has serious effects on the deep learning approach of MS students which keeps them away from achieving their goals and using their full potential in life. Many students engage in this behavior to some extent, and the majority of students openly acknowledge it as a problematic behavior (Tefula, 2014). Therefore, special attention should be paid to the different effects that procrastination has on the deep learning approach of MS students.

Understanding the root causes of procrastination and raising awareness about this problematic behavior is essential. Various scholars have identified mainly two forms of procrastination in students; Active procrastination and passive procrastination. Regardless of the specific type, procrastination leads to reduced student performance, fostering carelessness, laziness, passivity, and academic stagnation, ultimately making students less responsible (Sarwat & Irshad, 2010).

Furthermore, Procrastination negatively impacts the effectiveness of the deep learning approach. The deep learning approach involves intrinsic motivation, critical thinking,

connecting prior knowledge with new information, linking theoretical concepts with practical experiences, and focusing on getting knowledge beyond course requirements by using evidence and arguments. It typically occurs when students engage in higher-order tasks such as analysis, evaluation, and creation (Sagar, 2020).

Statement of the problem

Many researchers have explored procrastination across various areas of life, but there is a notable gap when it comes to investigating its impact on the deep learning approach within the specific context of Pakistan. The majority of the students tend to procrastinate especially at the MS level which affects their overall performance. Hence, to fill the gaps from previous research the present study aims to shed light on the effect of procrastination on the deep learning approach of MS students at IIUI.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were:

- To find out possible strategies used by MS-level students to overcome procrastination practices.
- To investigate the factors of procrastination on the deep learning approach of MS students
- To assess the effects of procrastination on the deep learning approach of MS students

Research Questions

Based on the objectives following questions were formulated;

- Which strategies can be used by MS students to overcome procrastination practice?
- What are the factors of procrastination in the deep learning approach of MS students?
- How does procrastination effect on deep learning approach of MS students?

Significance of the study

The present study will attempt to close the notable gap between educators and MS-level students. Educators can customize learning strategies to address and overcome procrastination tendencies among MS students by offering guidance on enhancing their approaches to learning. This research will guide MS-level students, enabling them to effectively address and improve their procrastination practices while enhancing their approach to learning.

Delimitation of the study

The study was delimited to female students of the MS program from the Educational Leadership and Management Department, Faculty of Education at IIUI.

Literature Review

The word —Procrastination| derives from the Latin words —Prol and —Crastinus" which means "forward or forth," and "tomorrow" (Balivada, 2020). Procrastination is a universally recognized and negative human behavior that most people are familiar with, either through personal experience or by observing it in others' lives. Procrastination involves delaying tasks, whether they are significant or trivial without considering the unpleasant results (Sirois, 2022). Chu and Choi (2005) proposed that procrastinating does not always result in undesirable outcomes (Chu & Choi, 2005). They distinguish it between the two forms of procrastination which are as follows:

Passive procrastination is a self-destructive process in which students do not intentionally delay tasks; rather, their inability to complete tasks on time or make wise decisions causes their tasks to run behind schedule. Unlike attractive ones, their attention is mostly focused on the critical duties at hand (Wambach, Steel, & Brothen, 2001). Active procrastination is a self-regulating time-management strategy in which students are

effective at finishing their activities within the allotted time, in contrast to passive procrastinators. When they reach deadlines, they feel energized, their motivation increases and they experience greater difficulties.

Several reasons and components influence students' learning outcomes. Particularly, university students have the lack of motivation, appropriate direction, problem-solving abilities, and time management skills. Studies on procrastination have also found that those who have a tendency to put things off are more likely to engage in activities that stimulate their interest. Fun activities can easily divert their attention. Students usually harm themselves by performing unnecessary tasks; as a result, they are self-handicapped. Consequently, the comfort zone serves as a psychological safety to them due to their ability to keep themselves away from stressful situations (Batool S. , 2020).

Moreover, procrastination is greatly influenced by social factors and it occurs when people often spend a lot of time with their friends and family because it makes them happy and they enjoy being together. As a result, they don't think much about stressful tasks or unpleasant events (Schraw, Wadkins, & Olafson, 2007). Besides, effective time management is crucial in the academic setting. It is not a skill that someone is born with; it's a skill that can progressively be enhanced over time. Students must, therefore, learn time management skills to overcome the effect of procrastination (Ackerman & Gross, 2005). Sometimes, procrastination can be characterized as a form of ineffective delay, frequently caused by a lack of initiative which refers to the general ability to energetically start tasks. Consequently, students who possess a strong tendency to take initiative tend to excel in the completion of tasks (Batool s. , 2018). Low Frustration Tolerance (LFT) is the major cause of distress. The LFT concept was

developed by psychologist Albert Ellis. This concept is associated with anxiety and a dislike of the work, both of which lead to procrastination. When tasks become more challenging and overwhelming, students tend to delay those tasks (Hoffrogge, 2001).

Additionally, laziness is also a major factor in contributing to procrastination. It involves a tendency to postpone or delay tasks. The person engaging in laziness may become distracted by a variety of interesting activities (Batool s. , 2018). In fact, the students' performance is significantly impacted by their low motivation, which serves as a primary cause of procrastination among them (Ackerman & Gross, 2005). If a person is fully committed to overcoming this negative behavior, they can overcome it with a boosted willpower. For self-motivated students, strengthening and focusing on their intrinsic motivations can easily reduce or completely eradicate their tendency to procrastinate (Brownlow & Reasinger, 2000). The procrastination practice may also result from illogical thoughts (Dietz, Hofer , & Fries, 2007). So, the low level of procrastination is typically seen in those students who can focus and are not distracted by noise or other distractions in their environment (Hoxbt, 2000). Another cause of procrastination among students is boredom and they stop working on a task after a while when given challenging tasks to start with. Easy tasks become easier to complete if one starts with a preference for them (Plessis, 2006). So, students must comprehend the significance of their work and begin with a prioritized list based on urgency and importance.

According to (Dilmac, 2009), students are likely to cope with frustration and stress because they recognize the significance of the tasks and they often use ways to deal with their stress. Students can eliminate the behavior that encourages them to put off finishing the task by adopting task-oriented strategies, focusing on the task at hand, and

minimizing stress-inducing behaviors. Emotionally strong students can effectively motivate themselves and reduce procrastination by addressing factors such as anxiety and the fear of failure through an emotionally focused approach. The avoidance-based approach is an additional tactic to stop the practice of putting off tasks. If someone uses this tactic to deal with procrastination, their stress level will drop considerably.

Chu & Choi (2005) claimed that because of the distractions, they are unable to identify a solution (Chu & Choi, 2005). Students often experience stress and anxiety, reacting to challenges and fearing future uncertainties. These emotions, like fear and constant worry, impact both mental and physical well-being. Research indicates that stress can lead to procrastination, as students may avoid challenging tasks. Surprisingly, stress can sometimes drive procrastinators to meet deadlines, causing anxiety but enhancing productivity (Batool s. , 2018).

Procrastination often results in lower exam grades, primarily due to heightened anxiety affecting academic performance. Negative outcomes, such as low- grade expectations and disorganized content, can hinder progress. Interestingly, active procrastinators may face more detrimental effects on academic performance than passive procrastinators. Procrastination isn't just laziness but a complex behavior influenced by emotions and actions. Overcoming procrastination requires self- reflection and a critical evaluation of one's performance (Batool s. , 2018).

Deep learning Approach

The concept of deep learning was first introduced by Marton and Säljö in 1976. Higher-order thinking abilities like synthesis and evaluation must be indicated as well as a genuine desire to learn the content rather than just memorizing facts to succeed. When motivation and attention prevail, deep learning—a thorough comprehension of

complex ideas—can occur. Pupils are more confident in their own skills (Cano & Berbén, 2009). A deep learning approach in which students attempt to connect the material to what they already know and are genuinely interested in what they are learning (Dolmans, Loyens, Marcq, & Gijbel, 2016). An individual's dedication to comprehending the subject matter through a variety of techniques, including reading, combining resources, debating concepts, and applying knowledge in a practical setting, represents deep learning (Hussin, Hamed, & Jam, 2017).

Research Methodology

The present study was qualitative in nature. The study was conducted at the International Islamic University Islamabad. The population of the study was 22 MS female students of the Educational Leadership and Management department from the Faculty of Education. A random sampling technique was used to select the students. A sample of 14 students was selected. The study has respondents from the first and second semesters of the MS ELM program. Semi-structured interviews were conducted for data collection purposes from the sample of the study. The interview guide consisted of fourteen (14) open-ended questions. A self-designed semi-structured interview was carried out to collect data from 14 students, aiming to understand the reasons behind their procrastination practices, the effects, and the strategies they employ to combat procrastination. The data was gathered by the researcher through in-person interviews with MS students at the International Islamic University Islamabad. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the respondents' consent and were audio-recorded. At the beginning of each interview, the researcher provided an overview of the research topic to the participants before delving into questions about the causes of procrastination and the strategies used to overcome this procrastination tendency. Each

interview had a duration of 10-15 minutes, and all the participants' responses were diligently documented and recorded. Thematic analysis technique was used for data analysis. Qualitative data analysis involved deriving themes from the scholars' responses, with the researcher using terms like "most" and "some" to analyze the responses of the participants.

Firstly, the obtained raw data was organized and documented. Similar keywords were consolidated within one theme. The various subthemes were combined under a single heading or major themes, supporting the development of the final themes.

THEMES

Causes	Effects	Strategies
procrastination	procrastination	Time management
Laziness	Lack of understanding	Set realistic goals
Poor time management	Workload	Set priorities
Distraction (family, social, political, job, family)	Mental stress	Follow schedule
Digital distraction	Poor performance	Motivation
Lack of motivation	Self-blame	Proper planning
Multi-tasking	Unsatisfactory study	Avoid multi-tasking
Feeling overwhelmed	Mismanagement	Eliminate distraction
Illogical thoughts	Lack of time	Social media distraction
Health issues	Reduce work quality	Task focused approach
Irregularity in scheduled	Critical thinking	Take break (self-relaxation)
Lack of guidance	Reduced research quality	Initiative
Self-motivation	Hinders creativity	
Perfectionism	Missing opportunities	
Learning habit		
Learning environment		

One of the respondents said that perfectionism is a factor for procrastination. She said —Yes, I procrastinate because I seek perfection in everything. I got bothered by any mistakes or unnecessary details in my tasks. Furthermore, when I begin a task, I want to address it comprehensively, striving for perfection. I have a habit of doing things perfectly, but I don't start right away because it's time-consuming, so I delay my work until the last minute. Unfortunately, at the last moment, I run out of time to achieve perfection, and I also face the pressure of meeting deadlines. As a result, I unintentionally overlook some concepts, and sometimes I intentionally skip due to time constraints.

Another respondent said that learning habit contributes to procrastination. She stated, —In my point of view the tendency to delay tasks can be influenced by both inherent traits and learned habits, and habitual procrastination may develop over time, potentially contributing to a persistent pattern of delaying actions.

One more respondent said that the learning environment acts as a factor for procrastination. She said —Yes, I often procrastinate and postpone my academic tasks until a later time because I face challenges when it comes to establishing a proper learning environment at home. Various factors, such as joyous or distressing moments, events, or gatherings, can disrupt their focus and hinder their ability to maintain a consistent study schedule. Effects of procrastination

It is analyzed through the responses of the majority of respondents that aspects such as lack of understanding, workload, mental stress, poor performance, and self-blame as the effects of procrastination. Some of the respondents consider aspects such as unsatisfactory study, mismanagement of time

Findings of the study

The interview responses of the MS scholars were about the following.

Causes of procrastination

It is analyzed through the responses of most respondents that aspects like laziness, poor time management, distraction (family, social, political, job, family), digital distraction, and lack of motivation as the reasons for procrastination. Some of the respondents consider aspects like multi-tasking, feeling overwhelmed, illogical thoughts, health issues, irregularity in schedules and lack of guidance as the reasons for the causes of procrastination.

and reduced work quality as the effects of procrastination.

One of the respondents said that procrastination affects my critical thinking. She said —Yes, procrastination significantly hampers critical thinking when adopting a deep learning approach, impeding the ability to engage thoughtfully and strategically in the complexities of the subject. This delay in tackling tasks related to deep learning can hinder understanding and hinder the development of essential analytical skills required for effective problem-solving in this field.

Another respondent said that procrastination reduced my research quality. She said —In my point of view procrastination adversely impacts the progress of a research thesis focused on a deep learning approach, impeding productivity, hindering timely completion, and potentially compromising the overall quality of the study.

One more respondent said that procrastination badly affects my creativity. She said —Yes, procrastination can negatively impact creativity in a deep learning approach by delaying the exploration of innovative ideas and hindering the iterative process essential for refining models. Timely engagement is crucial for experimenting with various architectures, optimizing hyper parameters, and incorporating novel techniques, all of which contribute to the creative evolution of deep learning models. Procrastination disrupts this flow, potentially impeding the development of cutting-edge solutions in the rapidly advancing field of deep learning. Another respondent said that due to procrastination I missed out on better opportunities. She said —In my point of view procrastination can lead to missed opportunities as individuals delay important tasks, hindering their ability to seize favorable moments. Whether it's procrastinating on job applications, project deadlines, or personal development, the cumulative effect may result

in passing up chances for career advancement, skill enhancement, or other valuable experiences. Over time, consistently putting things off can limit one's exposure to beneficial opportunities and hinder overall growth.

Strategies to overcome procrastination

Most respondents consider aspects such as Time management, setting realistic goals, setting priorities, creating a schedule, motivation, and proper planning as the strategies to overcome procrastination. Some of the respondents consider aspects such as avoiding multi-tasking, eliminating distraction, social media distraction, task-focused approach, and Taking breaks (self-relaxation) as the strategies to overcome procrastination.

One of the respondents said that avoiding multi-tasking is important to overcome procrastination. She stated —Yes, avoiding multitasking is a strategy to overcome procrastination because focusing on one task at a time allows for better concentration and productivity. When attention is divided among multiple activities, it can lead to a sense of overwhelm and hinder progress on important tasks. By dedicating focused time to each task, individuals can manage their workload more effectively, complete tasks efficiently, and reduce the likelihood of procrastination.

Another respondent said that taking initiative is an effective strategy to overcome procrastination as stated by her, —In my point of view some students find it challenging to initiate tasks, but once they start, they gain momentum and are reluctant to abandon their work midway, leading to satisfaction and enhanced comprehension.

Discussion

The findings of the present study are consistent with the consequences of procrastination, such as hindered critical thinking, compromised research quality, and missed opportunities for better outcomes,

emphasizing the need for addressing procrastination at both individual and institutional. While, a study conducted by Fentaw (2022) on academic procrastination in which he reported that procrastination leads to lower self-confidence, cheating, despair, and boredom (Fentaw, T, & M, 2022) . Additionally, the current study highlights the unique challenges faced by students in the specific academic context of International Islamic University Islamabad and found a variety of effects of academic procrastination, including lower performance, stress, and lower self-confidence. These findings are consistent with findings from a variety of studies that found many effects of procrastination, such as low self-confidence (Firouzeh & Jalil, 2011), poor academic performance (Fritzsche, Young, & Hickson, 2003) as well as high levels of anxiety and stress.

Furthermore, the current study identified the major causes of procrastination including social distraction, Laziness, and Digital distraction. Similarly, Fentaw (2022) claimed that similar reasons (social events, lethargy, and ineffective use of social media) were found in different study settings where the majority of the students are procrastinators (Fentaw, T, & M, 2022). However, in the current study, poor time management is considered one of the main reasons for students' procrastination in the context of a deep learning approach that supports the study of Fee and Tangney (2000), who demonstrated that procrastination is more than merely a time management issue (Fee & Tangney, 2000). In contradiction, Batool (2020) claimed that there is a psychological belief behind procrastination that is closely related to an individual's ability to complete tasks under stressful circumstances. So, this is the unique factor that was reported in the literature (Batool S. , 2020).

Besides, effective strategies to overcome procrastination, such as effective time

management, setting realistic goals, and adopting a task-oriented approach Dilmac (2009) resonate with existing literature on addressing the effects of procrastination on the deep learning approach (Dilmac, 2009). In doing so, we can adapt the deep learning approach to tackle procrastination by creating a conducive learning environment in classrooms and avoiding a multitasking approach.

Conclusions

Procrastination among MS students is a multifaceted issue influenced by factors such as laziness, poor time management, digital distractions, and overwhelming workloads. The consequences of procrastination range from increased mental stress to hindered critical thinking and compromised research quality. However, various effective strategies have been explored to overcome procrastination such as effective time management, realistic goal setting, and task-oriented approaches. Accordingly, we can implement these strategies, including breaking tasks into manageable steps and eliminating distractions to increase productivity and a proactive disciplined approach that minimizes procrastination tendencies. Ultimately, addressing procrastination not only improves academic performance but also positively impacts students' well-being and overall satisfaction with their work.

Recommendations

On the basis of findings and conclusions following recommendations were drawn. Students experience procrastination due to different reasons. So, it is recommended that students may avoid procrastination by using different strategies like taking initiative to organize themselves by making and following time table of study.

Procrastination has detrimental effects on academic success. So, it is recommended that

Institutions may organize seminars or conferences to inform students about negative impact and offer strategies.

Procrastination hinders timely completion and quality of a research thesis. So, it is recommended that teachers may include research-oriented activities to enhance active work habits.

Students often feel overwhelmed due to boring tasks, leading to reluctance in engaging with tasks. It is recommended that university may introduce a program to Overcome Procrastination to help students change their procrastination habits.

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